

INTERNATIONAL SEMINAR:

ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling
Approaches

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling Approaches: Book of Abstracts

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A Meta-Analysis of the *in vitro* Inhibitory Effects of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Dairy Products against Food-borne Pathogens

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Abstract

Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB) are a group of microorganisms that are commonly employed in dairy food production, bestowing desirable qualities like texture, aroma, and flavor, and possess bio-preservative features owing to their ability to produce lactic acid and peptides with antimicrobial properties. This review aimed to compile information concerning the *in vitro* antagonistic effect of LABs from dairy origin against selected food-borne pathogens. Electronic search used PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases to retrieve articles published from the year 2012 to 2022. A total of 12 primary studies passed the inclusion criteria and provided observations for *Listeria monocytogenes* (n = 123), *Staphylococcus aureus* (n = 107), and *Salmonella* Typhimurium (n = 45). The main outcome extracted was the mean inhibition zone in mm (ID) and its standard error (SE); and was subjected to univariate meta-analyses using the maximum likelihood method. Results showed that LAB from the *Enterococcus* genus presented the highest antagonistic activity against *L. monocytogenes* (pooled ID = 23.31 mm; SE = 2.59 mm). In addition, *Lactocaseibacillus* had the highest inhibitory effect against *Salmonella* Typhimurium (pooled ID = 14.90 mm; SE = 0.58 mm), while *Lactobacillus* presented the highest effect against *S. aureus* (pooled ID = 15.80 mm; SE = 1.16 mm). Moreover, inocula of *Lactococcus* genus presented the lowest inhibition activity against all three pathogens: *L. monocytogenes* (pooled ID = 11.40 mm; SE = 0.6 mm); *Salmonella* Typhimurium (pooled ID = 6.95 mm; SE = 0.23 mm); and *S. aureus* (pooled ID = 11.44 mm; SE = 0.68 mm). Further insights into specific indigenous dairy LAB with the greatest potential for inhibiting selected pathogens will be obtained through ongoing work.

Keywords: bio-preservation; antimicrobial capacity; inhibition zone; systematic review.

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